

THE FACTORS AFFECTING THE COMPETITIVENESS STRATEGY OF COASTAL SPORTS TOURISM INDUSTRY IN ZHUHAI CHINA

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Abstract

Coastal sports tourism is an emerging fashion field in the development of sports tourism industry. It is not only an important content of coastal tourism, but also an important branch of sports tourism. In 2013, coastal tourism accounted for more than 51% of China's total tourism revenue (Jiang, 2020, P2), and coastal leisure tourism has gradually become the most popular way of tourism. The research results will serve as one of the scientific theoretical and practical bases for the direct service of Zhuhai coastal sports tourism development strategy, which will contribute to the economic and social development of China, especially Zhuhai City, and also provide a basis for the implementation of the policies formulated by China's sports tourism management institutions. In addition, through the analysis and research of the coastal sports tourism industry, it is of great practical significance for the sports tourism enterprises to further realize their own competitive advantages and disadvantages, formulate practical development strategies, enhance the competitiveness of the enterprises, and promote the sustainable and rapid development of the enterprises. The research method of this paper is established based on the research questions and research objectives of the research object. Firstly, the advantages, disadvantages, opportunities and challenges of the development of coastal sports tourism in Zhuhai City are studied by using the SWOT analysis method, and then the impact is determined by the expert scoring method and the Delphi interview method. The factors for the development of coastal sports tourism in Zhuhai City, and then use the ANP-topsis analysis method to determine the priority and weight of the influencing factors. In the development strategy of coastal sports tourism in Zhuhai City, the independent variables usually include: production factors, demand conditions, and enterprise competition, related industries, and government behavior are the influencing factors of the five latitudes. The weights of these independent variables are determined by the ANP analysis method, and then input into the TOPSIS analysis method as the dependent variable for analysis, and finally the preferred projects and strategies are determined. At the same time, in the ANP-TOPSIS analysis method, it is also necessary to determine the hierarchical structure and mutual influence relationship between the variables in order to obtain more accurate results. The dependent variable Y=willingness to participate in Zhuhai coastal sports tourism, the independent variable X=influencing factors of Zhuhai coastal sports tourism, a=priority index of Zhuhai coastal sports tourism impression factors, b=other characteristics of tourism participants.

Keywords: Coastal Sports Tourism Industry, Competitiveness Strategy, Zhuhai.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 statement and significance of problem

Sports tourism is a very meaningful topic. It is increasingly popular, and gradually becomes a very charming leisure lifestyle. Nowadays, sports tourism from all over the world rises. People from all directions travel to sports tourism destinations. In sports tourism, people can not only experience thrilling excitement, but also feel elegant classics, but also enjoy the charm of high-end technology, and even taste the essence of national flavor.

Sports tourism enriches people's life content in highlighting people's distinctive activities and broadens people's leisure field. Sports tourism consumption has gradually become the highlight of the tourism market consumption, and the trend has also become the hot spot in the sports market consumption.

Coastal sports tourism is a new industry in the period of rapid economic, social and cultural development in China. It is a high-end product of sports tourism and leisure vacation. The "proposal of the CPC Central Committee on formulating the 12th Five Year Plan for national economic and social development" adopted at the Fifth Plenary Session of the 17th CPC Central Committee clearly puts forward the need to develop the marine economy, adhere to the overall planning of land and sea, formulate and implement marine development strategies, and improve the ability of marine development (Ma, 2021, P2), control and comprehensive management.

Coastal sports tourism is an emerging fashion field in the development of sports tourism industry. It is not only an important content of coastal tourism, but also an important branch of sports tourism. In 2013, coastal tourism accounted for more than 51% of China's total tourism revenue (Jiang, 2020, P2), and coastal leisure tourism has gradually become the most popular way of tourism. According to relevant statistics, tourism has become an important industry or pillar industry in some coastal areas.

The development of China's sports tourism industry has been paid great attention to by the national and local government administrative departments. According to incomplete statistics, there are six national level documents and two related reports in the sports tourism industry.

After the introduction of relevant national policies, some provinces (cities) in China have issued new plans and measures to promote the development of the sports tourism industry, and more than 20 provinces (cities and autonomous regions) have given priority to their development as pillar industries or key industries (Zhang, 2022, P.30).

Zhuhai, Guangdong province has complex landform features, many islands, 146, coastline of 166.32 kilometers, according to the National tourism Administration statistics, the 2018 domestic tourism 5.539 billion, up 10.8% compared with the same period last year, achieve tourism revenue of 5.79 trillion yuan, up 10.5% year on year, the tourism market stability.

After the release of the development plan for the Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macao Greater Bay Area, Zhuhai received 43.1131 million tourists in 2018, up 8.3% year on year (Chen, 2019, P3) ; the total tourism revenue reached 46.616 billion yuan, up 26.8% year on year. The tourism industry has become an important pillar of the social and economic development of Zhuhai.

Figure 1: Geographical Location of Zhuhai City

On the one hand, the topic selection of this article is influenced by the macro environment of sports tourism development at home and abroad, and on the other hand, it is also related to the current theoretical research on the competitiveness of the sports tourism industry. The practical development needs and theoretical research lag of the sports tourism industry determine the topic selection of this article.

Figure 2: Location of Zhuhai Island Branch

The research results will serve as one of the scientific theoretical and practical bases for the direct service of Zhuhai coastal sports tourism development strategy, which will contribute to the economic and social development of China, especially Zhuhai City, and also provide a basis

for the implementation of the policies formulated by China's sports tourism management institutions. In addition, through the analysis and research of the coastal sports tourism industry, it is of great practical significance for the sports tourism enterprises to further realize their own competitive advantages and disadvantages, formulate practical development strategies, enhance the competitiveness of the enterprises, and promote the sustainable and rapid development of the enterprises.

1.2 Research Question

- 1) What are the elements and mechanisms of competitiveness strategy of coastal sports tourism industry in Zhuhai, China?
- 2) What is the development process of competitiveness strategy of coastal sports tourism industry in Zhuhai, China?
- 3) What are the factors affecting the competitiveness strategy of coastal sports tourism industry in Zhuhai, China influence?

1.3 Research Objective

- 1) To study the development process of competitiveness strategy of coastal sports tourism industry in Zhuhai, China?
- 2) To analyst the factors affecting the competitiveness strategy of coastal sports tourism industry in Zhuhai, China influence?
- 3) To develop the competitiveness model of coastal sports tourism industry in Zhuhai, China influence?

2. BODY OF PAPER

The analysis of the operation mechanism of sports tourism industry mainly includes four components: operation platform, operation factors, operation mechanism and operation objectives. Each component interacts and correlates with each other, deeply describes the internal laws of sports tourism industry, and vividly depicts the operation mechanism of sports tourism industry. Among them, the operation platform plays an important carrier role in the operation of sports tourism industry; Operation factors refer to the influencing factors of operation, which always affect the operation process of sports tourism industry; The operation mechanism is the internal embodiment of the operation of sports tourism industry; The operation goal is the final result of the operation of sports tourism industry.

The operation platform constitutes an important carrier for the operation of sports tourism industry and plays an important basic supporting role in the operation of sports tourism industry. Various forms of sports tourism industry activities can be realized on the operation platform. As an important part of the operation system of sports tourism industry, the operation platform mainly includes two basic types: entity platform and network platform, which continuously support the operation mechanism and realize various functions. Operation factors, as the influencing factors of the operation of sports tourism industry, affect the operation effect

of sports tourism industry, guide the development direction of sports tourism industry and determine the development vitality of sports tourism industry. Overall, the operation factors of sports tourism industry mainly include two basic types: Macro Influencing Factors and Micro Influencing Factors. The influencing factors at different levels together constitute an important part of the sports tourism industry system. The operation mechanism expounds the basic principle of the operation of sports tourism industry, which is the core link in the operation process of sports tourism industry, including six sub parts: Operation premise, operation foundation, operation path, operation mode, operation power and operation guarantee. The operation mechanism takes sports resources as the operation premise, tourism system elements as the operation basis, innovation drive as the operation driving force, government functions, industrial policies and regional economy as the operation guarantee, and forms a diversified operation mode of coordinated development, special development and industrial integration through a variety of operation paths such as demand-oriented, technology integration and resource embedding.

The operation goal is the ultimate goal of the sports tourism industry operation system and the final result of the sports tourism industry system. It reflects the output effect of the sports tourism industry operation system and affects the improvement and optimization of the sports tourism industry system. The operation objectives of sports tourism industry mainly include improving national quality, promoting industrial upgrading, giving full play to industrial advantages, perfecting industrial chain, building industrial system and so on.

Figure: Research framework

The research method of this paper is established based on the research questions and research objectives of the research object. Firstly, the advantages, disadvantages, opportunities and challenges of the development of coastal sports tourism in Zhuhai City are studied by using the SWOT analysis method, and then the impact is determined by the expert scoring method and

the Delphi interview method. The factors for the development of coastal sports tourism in Zhuhai City, and then use the ANP-topsis analysis method to determine the priority and weight of the influencing factors. In the development strategy of coastal sports tourism in Zhuhai City, the independent variables usually include: production factors, demand conditions, and enterprise competition, related industries, and government behavior are the influencing factors of the five latitudes.

The weights of these independent variables are determined by the ANP analysis method, and then input into the TOPSIS analysis method as the dependent variable for analysis, and finally the preferred projects and strategies are determined. At the same time, in the ANP-TOPSIS analysis method, it is also necessary to determine the hierarchical structure and mutual influence relationship between the variables in order to obtain more accurate results. The dependent variable Y=willingness to participate in Zhuhai coastal sports tourism, the independent variable X=influencing factors of Zhuhai coastal sports tourism, a=priority index of Zhuhai coastal sports tourism impression factors, b=other characteristics of tourism participants.

Figure: Research method and process

3. CONCLUSION

This article divides the factors that affect the competitiveness of China's sports tourism industry into five categories based on the "diamond model": production factors, market demand, related industries, enterprise competition, and government behavior. Based on this, a preliminary research framework is constructed to further summarize the development strategies of coastal sports tourism in Zhuhai.

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